

University of
Southern
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MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND DAMAGE ANALYSIS OF BRAIDED CFRP COMPOSITE REBAR

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Summary

Rebars

- ✓ Used as reinforcement in concrete.
- ✓ Improve the tensile strength
- ✓ Resist forces like bending, stretching, and cracking.

Concrete

Excellent: Compression strength

Poor: Tensile strength, prone to cracking

Concrete + Rebar

- ✓ **Significantly Stronger**
- ✓ **Prevent cracks from forming and spreading**
- ✓ **Increased Durability**

Work Offices

Residential

Industrial

Industrial

Bridges

Rebars used in Mining tunnels

- The conventional standard choice is Steel Rebar.
- High Ductility
- Low initial cost
- Can be bent and cut on-site

Drawbacks

- ❑ Low corrosive protection and compromise properties over a period of time.
- ❑ Heavy

FRP composites rods

- Light-weight
- No corrosion
- No fatigue
- Optimum strength in fibre direction

Quasi-isotropic Material

Methodology

Carbon Braided Rope

Braided CFRP Composite Rebar

Carbon Fibre Braiding

- ✓ Braiding Machine – 84/60 carriers
- ✓ Carbon Filament – 24k
- ✓ Wound 60 bobbins for braiding
- ✓ Carbon braided rope dia – 22 mm

**Bobbin
Winding
Unit**

Front View

Side View

Fixed Length CFRP Composites Rebar

- ✓ Material: Carbon Braided rope
- ✓ Resin/Hardener: Epoxy resin system
- ✓ Mix ratio and Curing time: Provided by supplier
- ✓ Carbon Fibre Rebar successfully made with and without Ribs:
 - 24 mm diameter with Ribs
 - 22 mm diameter without Ribs.

Interface

Carbon Braided rope

Mold with Ribs

Mold with Threads

Rein + hardener ↓

Comparison of Tensile Capacity

Sample	Rebar Material	XS area (mm ²)	Ultimate Tensile Peak Load (kN)	Normalised Specific Tensile peak load (kN/mm ² XS area relative M24)	Displacement at Peak load (mm)	Mass per metre (g/m)
M24 Steel Rock Rebar	Steel	378	325	325	56.35	2900
20-tonne fibreglass Rebar*	Glass Fibre	310	200	244	14.86	645
Braided CRFP Rebar	Carbon Fibre	285	236	313	29.2	465

* P. Gregor, A. Mirzaghorbanali, K. McDougall, N. Aziz, and B. Jodeiri Shokri, "Shear Behaviour of Fibreglass Rock Bolts for Various Pretension Loads," Rock Mech. Rock Eng., vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 8083–8113, Nov. 2023

Comparison of Single Shear Capacity of 20-tonne Glass Fibre and Braided Carbon Composites Rebar

Sample	Rebar Material	XS area (mm ²)	Average Shear Peak Load (kN)	Displacement at Peak load (mm)	Normalised Shear peak load (kN)
20-tonne fibreglass Rebar *	Glass Fibre	310	39.3	7.11	48
Braided CRFP Rebar	Carbon Fibre	285	75.03	13.56	100

* P. Gregor, A. Mirzaghorbanali, K. McDougall, N. Aziz, and B. Jodeiri Shokri, "Shear Behaviour of Fibreglass Rock Bolts for Various Pretension Loads," Rock Mech. Rock Eng., vol. 56, no. 11, pp. 8083–8113, Nov. 2023

Guillotine Double Shear Testing

- without-rib: sample1
- Without-rib:sample2
- Without-rib:sample3
- Without-rib:sample4
- without-rib:sample5

Sample 5 – Without Rib

Guillotine Double Shear Apparatus

- with-ribs:sample1
- with-ribs:sample2
- with-ribs:sample3
- with-ribs:sample4
- with-ribs:Sample5
- with-ribs:Sample6

Sample 5 – With Rib

Guillotine Double Shear results

Sample No.	Displacement at Maximum Load (mm)	Maximum Double Shear Load (kN)	F Shear Plane (kN)	Carbolt Diameter (mm)	τ (ratio between shear force and cross-section area) (Mpa)	
Without Rib	Sample1	13.833	153.4	76.7	29.49	112.29
	Sample2	13.562	145.5	72.75	29.16	108.67
	Sample3	16.048	161.4	80.7	28.73	124.48
	Sample4	14.072	146.9	73.45	27.34	125.11
	Sample5	12.98	146.7	73.35	28.1	118.28
With Rib	Sample1	11.8	128	64	24.12	140.1
	Sample2	11.7	161	80.5	23.97	178.5
	Sample3	17.1	149.2	74.6	24.29	160.9
	Sample4	14.2	161.8	80.9	24.19	176.2
	Sample5	15.4	151.1	75.55	24.31	162.9
	Sample6	11.2	149.3	74.65	23.95	165.8

Tensile Strength Testing

Pull-out Testing

150mm-200mm
pull-out specimen

100-150mm
pull-out specimen

Damage Analysis during Pull-out testing

Summary

- ✓ The testing results shows that Braided Carbon FRP composites Rebar (Carbolt) as viable alternative or complement to the traditional Steel rock bolts.
- ✓ Although, prototype demonstrated strengths, yet there are further refinement to achieve full commercial viability.
- ✓ In terms of single shear strength, the braided CFRP composite Rebar was lower than M24 Steel rock bolt but remained superior to that of glass fibre rebar. The use of braided carbon fibre contributed to the higher normalized single shear strength, improving load bearing capacity, and energy absorption.
- ✓ The braided CFRP composite rebar performed well in tensile strength when its specific strength was normalized for cross-sectional area. The results suggests that with further optimization of the carbon fibre content, the braided CFRP composite rebar could match or exceed the tensile strength of steel rockbolt.
- ✓ Overall the results suggest that the braided CFRP composite rebar has significant potential as a corrosion-resistant, light weight, alternative to steel rock bolts.

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Thank You!

Any questions?

